

CREATING AN OPEN-SOURCE HARDWARE ECOSYSTEM FOR RESEARCH AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

At the core of education, engineering, and science lies the quest to better understand and improve the world. This document aims to explain the essential role of open-source hardware for this mission and why it should be considered an essential pillar of the ongoing open science programmes in Dutch Universities.

Open-source hardware is hardware whose design is made publicly available so that anyone can study, modify, distribute, make, and sell the design or other hardware and products based on that design. Ideally, the design of open source hardware is available in the preferred format for making modifications and uses widely available components and materials, standard processes, open infrastructure, unrestricted content, and open-source design tools to maximize the ability of other individuals to make and use hardware. Open-source hardware gives people the freedom to control their technology while sharing knowledge and encouraging commerce through the open exchange of (compatible) designs.

Open Science practices are becoming the norm in academia, and are rightly encouraged by funders and policymakers of higher education. Open-source hardware is an essential pillar of Open Science. Sharing hardware designs openly both enables more people and teams to access it, and through encouraging replication it makes science more reproducible. But it is also an area of contention because of the exclusive knowledge transfer practices and (not always justified) confidentiality clauses in research partnerships or contract defaults.

Beyond academia, open hardware has the potential to radically transform science, education, and society by facilitating collaborative innovation and democratizing access to technology. It can massively accelerate the transition of an invention into a useful product, and simultaneously reduce costs and promote sustainable practices. By promoting open-source hardware initiatives, the Netherlands can solidify its position as a leader in Open Science and contribute to the global effort of achieving the sustainable development goals.

This white paper aims to provide a comprehensive guideline for the implementation of open source hardware initiatives in the Netherlands, particularly in academia. The paper will discuss how bottom-up initiatives at universities can be orchestrated with top-down governance from universities and research organizations, such as NWO and KNAW, to maximize the benefits of open-source hardware in science, education, and society.

We highlight some projects that are benefiting from implementation of open science practices applied to hardware. We further discuss components of a strategy that could lead to the creation of a flourishing ecosystem for open-source scientific hardware in the Netherlands, that increases the quality and impact of research and education, and is symbiotically related to the global Open Science movement.

We also acknowledge that some special technologies, such as specialized medical care and military equipment, are less compatible with open hardware due to issues that come from economic constraints, geopolitics, security, ethics, and so on.

The goal of this white paper is to provide a consistent narrative on the opportunities and capabilities arising from embracing open-source hardware from both national and international perspectives. The authors of this paper call for increasing the attention and allocating more national resources to support open hardware projects.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 1959, the Volvo engineer Nils Bohlin developed the modern three-point seat belt. Although the design was patented, the company decided the patent was to be left open, making it available to all vehicle manufacturers to use for free. This rather unconventional decision was made in the greater interest of public safety, to ensure that everyone, independently of whether they drove a Volvo or not, could be safer in traffic. At the time of Bohlin's death in September 2002, Volvo estimated that the seat belt had saved more than one million lives in the four decades since it was introduced.

In 1922, injection of insulin was successfully tested as an effective remedy for type-1 diabetes, a deadly disease at the time. For their discovery of insulin, Frederick Banting and John Macleod were awarded the 1923 Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine. The research team sold the patent for insulin to the University of Toronto for \$1 each. Banting famously stated, "Insulin does not belong to me, it belongs to the world."¹ In the past two decades, in the United States, this life-saving medicine has reached such disproportionately high prices that patients are reportedly choosing between their medicine and other essential life supplies such as food and shelter. The rising cost of insulin in the United States is attributed primarily to the limitless pricing policies and lack of competition between the pharmaceutical providers who are given legal protection for their proprietary insulin products.

In both cases of the seat-belt and insulin, the inventors and discoverer had intended to put their mark on humanity by providing public access. However, the incremental innovations made on insulin are patented by companies and are leading to price gouging. The contrasting current state of the two products demonstrates the insufficiency of the current intellectual property protection to fulfill the desires of the inventors and researchers, opposite to what was intended by these regulations. In the face of rising global and national inequalities of access to life-saving technologies, many scholars and policy makers are calling for a fundamental revision of the traditional tech transfer policies in publicly funded research institutions, to realize the highest positive impact of their innovations on the citizens and the society at large.

The technological transformations required for sustainability and global health increase the urgency of a widespread reconsideration of the role of open science and open hardware in dissemination of publicly financed research and higher education. The recent experience of the COVID-19 pandemic has demonstrated that conventional supply chains for most essential products can easily fail the urgent needs of the people. At the same time, distributed manufacturing enabled by digital fabrication combined with open-source quality control has been proven life-saving. This recent case shows that even from an economic perspective, the most beneficial route to making technology accessible to the users can be based on open source hardware.

The world leaders call for adoption of Open Science practices

These experiences and observations are stated as the foreground for one of the most prominent calls for global adoption of Open Science practices in the complete cycle of creation, evaluation, and

dissemination of scientific knowledge and output. In this statement, issued by the General Conference of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) in 2021, these concrete recommendations on Open Science were adopted:

1. promoting a common understanding of open science, associated benefits and challenges, as well as diverse paths to open science;
2. developing an enabling policy environment for open science;
3. investing in open science infrastructures and services;
4. investing in human resources, training, education, digital literacy and capacity building for open science;
5. fostering a culture of open science and aligning incentives for open science;
6. promoting innovative approaches for open science at different stages of the scientific process;
7. promoting international and multi-stakeholder cooperation in the context of open science and with view to reducing digital, technological and knowledge gaps.

In the UNESCO recommendations, **open hardware** is one of the five pillars of open scientific knowledge, next to **scientific publications**, **open research data**, **open educational resources**, and **open-source software**.

While this declaration highlights the international recognition of the open hardware movement as the favored path forward for scientific activities, many researchers (see Box 1 for an example of a researcher's perspective), associations, and even philanthropic organizations have called for embracing open hardware as the default or recommended route for development of research hardware for and by researchers. Open Hardware Trailblazers Fellowships from the Open-Source Hardware Association (OSHW), Supplyframe's Hackaday Prize, the Prototype Fund of the Open Knowledge Foundation, Open Science policy at CERN, the Open Metrology initiative supported by NIST and MIT's Center for Bits and Atoms, and the open source policy of the Chan Zuckerberg's Initiative are a few notable examples.

The national Open Science program in the Netherlands is internationally recognized as one of the best organized and comprehensive open science programs. It has benefited a lot from bottom-up initiatives such as the open science communities, the national open science festival, and several university-specific programs. While, historically, (digital) access to research output and data infrastructures have been the driving force behind many open science initiatives, standardization and interoperability of **research hardware** is increasingly seen as a major component of realization of transformative open science ambitions.

Despite the national prominence of open science in the Netherlands, exemplified by the recent establishment of the OpenScienceNL organization, the role of open source hardware for research, design, education, and scientific value creation in general, is not sufficiently emphasized, and this important pillar is missing in the formalized policy documents.

In this white paper, we aim to provide an overview of the capabilities of open source hardware for open science, advancing research and education, and creating direct societal impact.

¹ N Engl J Med 2019; 381:1793-1795 DOI: 10.1056/NEJMp1909402

BOX 1: THE PERSPECTIVE OF THE RESEARCHERS

Dr Richard Bowman
University of Glasgow

Dr Richard Bowman is a Royal Society University Research Fellow specializing in microscopy and open hardware. His research group at the University of Bath is at the heart of the OpenFlexure project, which he started in 2015 while a research fellow in Cambridge University. The following perspective is an excerpt from his talk at the focus session: Open Hardware for Research at the NWO Physics conference in April 2023

“...The currently prominent mode of technology creation out of fundamental research is as follows: I have an idea. I developed my idea. At some point that idea is well enough developed to disclose it to my tech transfer office. If they like it, then they will patent it. That gives us some measure of protection that nobody else is allowed to use the idea without our permission. We then license that patent to a company, the company does some manufacturing. In fact, the company probably has to do about 10 times as much work in R&D as I did developing the idea in the first place. That company can potentially generate some revenue. And if we've gotten the paperwork right, some of that money flows back to research. But, in order for this to work, the first half of that process has to be secret, because many of the current partnership schemes are geared towards secrecy and non-disclosure. The second part of the process is generally exclusive because that allows the company to take on investment and to manage the risk of creating a new product. However this is a very leaky pipeline and many projects are abandoned.

An alternative pathway: I have the idea, I immediately share the idea before the idea is patentable. That means there are a lot more brains that can work on the project. Nothing stops a company coming along using that non-exclusive license and manufacturing it. And in fact, people can still make money this way or from services [see Opentrons example in Box 2]. But your colleagues can also reproduce the hardware or make it suitable for their experiments. The open license gives you the confidence that if you develop something exciting based on your invention at a later stage, you are not then going to be embroiled in lots of nasty litigation. Furthermore, because you shared this early, the community can start improving it and you can benefit from that as well.

It is not difficult to argue that the majority of scientific instruments are not suitable for mass commercial use. Therefore, the benefits of doing it openly, far outweigh the relatively small chance of commercial success by keeping everything secret. While the cost of keeping the invention or some details secret are huge for the advancement of science and obviously waste a lot of resources that could be spent on training and exploratory research...”

2. OPEN-SOURCE HARDWARE WITHIN THE CONTEXT OF OPEN SCIENCE

Worldwide, Open Science is a standard requirement for grants and publications. However, Open hardware is still not receiving adequate attention, particularly in the Netherlands, despite being a crucial component of Open Science. While Open Science is typically considered a "digital" issue, Open-source hardware involves physical components that must be open, repeatable, reproducible, and ideally, FAIR.

A widely accepted definition of open-source hardware, formalized by the OSHWA association, reads:

"The hardware's source, the design from which it is made, is available in the preferred format for making modifications to it [...] open-source hardware gives people the freedom to control their technology while sharing knowledge and encouraging commerce through the open exchange of designs."

In general open hardware or open-source hardware² shares the same principles as Open Science - transparency, collaboration, and accessibility in scientific research. It promotes sharing hardware designs, schematics, and specifications, enabling the replication, modification, and enhancement of scientific equipment and experimental setups. A famous example of open-source hardware is the Arduino microcontroller, which started as an educational project and has revolutionized digitally-controlled devices such as 3D-printers and robotic instruments. Some Arduino-controlled devices have even been used as life-saving equipment during the recent COVID-19 global pandemic.

Open-source hardware can advance the goals of Open Science in several tangible ways. Use of openly shared hardware designs promotes **transparency** in experimental setups, measurements, and results. Open hardware also enables replication of experiments and verification of measurement results. Working with commonly available and replicable scientific instrumentation obviously facilitates **collaboration** and knowledge exchange among scientists, accelerating scientific progress. This approach also contributes to the **accessibility** of scientific research. In many cases, traditional scientific equipment can be expensive and proprietary, making them hard to access for researchers with limited resources. On the other hand, open hardware designs can be more affordable and accessible, empowering a broader community to engage in scientific experimentation, and enhancing the democratization of science.

Furthermore, open-source hardware encourages **innovation** and

customization. Researchers and developers can modify existing designs or develop new hardware solutions tailored to their needs. This flexibility enables them to address unique research questions and challenges, increasing creativity and pushing the boundaries of scientific exploration. It also helps with the sustainability of research hardware and avoiding obsolescence or research waste.

Open hardware is an ideal facilitator of Open Science because it adheres to its principles while dealing with tangible products. Researchers can promote transparency, collaboration, reproducibility, accessibility, and innovation by sharing hardware designs. This approach strengthens the foundation of Open Science, leading to the advancement of scientific knowledge and benefiting the scientific community as a whole.

Considering the knowledge-based inventions coming out of publicly funded research, the effectiveness of the conventional secrecy-based privatization and market-led technology transfer is questionable, from a research-ethics and public policy perspective. The consideration of fairness and equitable access is especially important for innovations regarding an equitable access to the basic living standards and sustainable living. These points have been raised by the economist Mariana Mazzucato, who is advising multiple UK, EU, and international bodies on public sector innovation:

*"All too often, we are lazy about partnerships. Just because you have "partnered" does not mean that you are working well together for the common good, which requires also setting the objective together and aligning risks and rewards. All parties must be on the same page about the "what" in addition to the "how." That is how you not only develop vaccines but also make them accessible to all. With a common-good approach, each step of the process is almost as important as the final result."*³

² On the distinction between terms Open Hardware and Open-Source Hardware see <https://www.oshwa.org/research/brief-history-of-open-source-hardware-organizations-and-definitions/>

³ For the Common Good, Mariana Mazzucato, Jan 27 2023

<https://www.project-syndicate.org/commentary/common-good-governance-key-elements-by-mariana-mazzucato-2023-01>

3. PERSISTENT IMPACT OF OPEN-SOURCE HARDWARE PROJECTS

Demystifying the perception of open-source hardware related to its quality and impact

For over 25 years, the term "open-source hardware" has been in use. Similar to open-source software, open-source hardware allows others to study, modify, create, and distribute design files. The formation and growth of a global community of open hardware developers have resulted in numerous amazing projects. While it's impossible to provide an exhaustive list of influential projects within this white paper, we have selected a few frontrunners from various fields to showcase the strength and diversity within open source hardware. Even a brief look at these projects is sufficient to acknowledge their high quality and worldwide impact.

The Delft University open hardware community is maintaining a long list of useful projects and resources, with an emphasis on education.

Examples of influential open-source hardware projects around the world

Education: Arduino, the de facto standard for electronics enthusiasts, serves as an excellent platform for electronics education and prototyping. It originated in Italy as a solution for simple electronics education and has since evolved into a highly-trusted and successful company.

Manufacturing: Opulo, an automated pick-and-place machine for assembling surface-mount devices (SMD) components on a PCB, stands out in the field of manufacturing by facilitating mid-scale production.

Research: Open source research hardware is also widely used in academia. One example is the OpenFlexure project, a commonly employed optical microscope that can be easily transported to the field, replicated, and modified.

Biology: Open hardware projects are also represented in the field of biology and medical research, take for example Opentrons, a lab liquid handling robot, that enables rapid and reliable pipetting, and its availability of source files allows for easy study and modification. (see Box 2)

Healthcare: Open hardware projects play a crucial role in accessibility of healthcare. Recently the first open-source MRI scanner has been presented, the OSI2 ONE, it is a project from the bigger Open Source

Imaging community, which aims to provide greater access to medical imaging for patients around the world.

Environmental safety: Open hardware has long been associated with citizen science. Following the earthquake and disasters in Hiroshima, the Safecast project collected valuable and more accurate radiation data in Japan than what the government could provide at the time. The open source nature of the project allowed for rapid scalability.

Engineering: Open hardware is commonly used in engineering for quickly manufacturing 3D printed parts. A notable example is the Prusa 3D printers, which are industrial-grade printers capable of printing complex 3D models. The printers have an active open community that continually improves their performance.

Computing: RISC-V processors provide the closest link to open source software. These open hardware designed integrated circuits (ICs) offer transparency in their functioning and contribute to democratizing the chip manufacturing industry.

Automation: Olimex has been a persistent player in the field of open source embedded electronics for more than 25 years, originating from Bulgaria they have developed many microprocessors with focus on the automation of industry.

The Open Source Stories produced by the Red Hat company present an extensive and visually inviting overview of some impactful open source projects.

Institutions supporting open-source hardware

The success and reliability of open source research hardware is acknowledged by international organizations. CERN, for example, has played a pioneering role in introducing Open Source Hardware (OSHW) to physics and beyond. Their continued support is emphasized in the official Open Science policy statement of CERN:

“CERN makes its technologies broadly available to society and introduced open hardware licensing as a key mechanism to achieve this goal. Open hardware designs are made available through the Open Hardware Repository. The legal basis for sharing of open hardware is enabled through variants of the CERN Open Hardware Licence. Hardware design releases will consider opportunities for collaboration

BOX 2: THE SUCCESS OF OPENTRONS

Opentrons
Biotechnology company

Opentrons is a company that produces laboratory robots designed to automate experiments based on the open source 3D printing framework. From the outset, their robots are designed to be affordable and accessible, allowing researchers to focus on their work rather than manual pipetting.

In 2019, when the Covid-19 pandemic hit New York very hard and the limited test capacity was not enough to cover even a small fraction of the patients, Opentrons succeeded

in adjusting their robots to automate the process of testing patient samples for the virus, allowing researchers to process more samples more quickly, all in a few days.

The cost reduction of each test from \$2000 to \$14 was a significant achievement, as it helped make testing more affordable and accessible to a larger population. Additionally, the reduced duration of testing from 20 days to less than 24 hours allowed for quicker results, enabling individuals to receive prompt medical attention and reducing the spread of the virus.

At almost the same time, the testing capacity in the Netherlands was severely reduced due to the limited availability of the proprietary buffer from the exclusive provider company, despite the well-equipped national health services (GGD).

The impact of Opentrons' efforts during the pandemic cannot be overstated. Their contribution in increasing testing capacity has helped in saving numerous lives. Their work is a testament to the power of open source innovation and collaboration.

The evident contrast between the impact of open source vs proprietary technologies during a crisis, shows that the old technology transfer paradigm, based on secrecy and privately owned companies, needs revision.

with other research communities and industry. In cases where extensive documentation and ancillary components like software for interfacing and testing are required for projects, these should be licensed under appropriate open source documentation and software licenses respectively.”

More recently, following on Biden Administration’s Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) declaration of 2023 as the year of Open Science, the Wilson Center and the Open Environmental Data Project convened a roundtable to outline a roadmap for open science hardware to be fully integrated into environmental monitoring at all levels of government in the US.⁴ This movement is in line with the adopted policies of NASA for supporting Open Science, open-source software, and open data as the default for its programs, and more recently with the Open Source Science Initiative (OSSI). It is notable that this NASA program has co-organized the open science summit of July 2023, together with CERN.

Even some private funders have embraced open source products as their primary means of creating impact. For example, the EnAccess foundation, which focuses on renewable electricity production and distribution, funds only open source hardware projects or and open access technologies because their “goal is to save energy access companies time and money.”

The emerging open-source hardware movement in the Netherlands

OSHWA has certified more than 2300 open-source hardware projects, worldwide. There are merely 14 projects from the Netherlands in this list, which is underwhelming, especially when considering the high level of knowledge production and invention disclosures from Dutch universities and knowledge institutions. With the exception of a few notable examples, the open source hardware movement in the Netherlands is still at its infancy, and has not yet been acknowledged as a pillar of open science. There are a few examples that have succeeded in gaining national attention. This is mostly because of personal initiatives and a few sympathetic funding programs such as the Centre for Unusual

Collaborations, The Waag, Delft Open Science program, or the NWO Open Science Fund. The initial positive reaction to these projects can, however, be an indicator to the potential traction of such projects when they can get institutional backing.

Environmental monitoring: The Plastic Scanner project, originating in Delft, enables users to identify different types of plastic through discrete infrared spectroscopy. This technology helps individuals and companies sort plastic more efficiently and with greater traceability.

Housing: The Wikihouse community in Almere is spearheading the construction of new, innovative housing in an open source manner. By utilizing CNC-routed wooden panels, the buildings can be prefabricated, disassembled, and sourced from emission-neutral wood.

Recycling: Precious Plastic designs simple yet effective plastic recycling machines, empowering individuals worldwide to address the significant challenges of plastic pollution and start their own local plastic recycling businesses.

Energy storage: The FAIR battery project from Utrecht opens up redox energy storage methods to the public. It aims to facilitate distributed manufacturing and maintenance of electrochemical batteries by using widely available materials, making them suitable for off-grid energy storage despite their lower energy density.

Molecular biology: Driven by the Covid pandemic, a project was born for a fast, cheap, low-waste, and instrument-free detection of DNA and RNA. The T-Cup project uses just boiling water, a coffee capsule, and a 3D printed holder, for the detection of nucleic acid in different samples.

Laboratory instruments: In this project cheap consumer-grade 3D printers are turned into functional laboratory instruments. Two examples are using the 3D-printers parts and software to fabricate Open Hardware syringe pumps, and a robot for performing histology slides named HistoEnder.

While these examples demonstrate the great potential and capabilities of open-source hardware projects, this strength has not been used systematically for the common purpose of advancing science in and serving the society by public research institutions.

4. WHY OPEN-SOURCE HARDWARE SHOULD BE PART OF EVERY UNIVERSITY'S AGENDA

The common thread that connects most of the open hardware projects mentioned in this paper are the strong emphasis of the project collaborators on societal impact. There are at least five areas where open hardware projects enable organizations to have a major impact:

- **Social empowerment** by democratizing knowledge, tools and resources
- **Distributed economic growth** by inspiring others to make derivatives, start new companies and increase competitiveness of established companies,
- **Distributed technical advancement** by accelerating innovations, introducing new methods as continuous development with version control
- **Environmental sustainability** by making repairs simpler, preventing vendor lock-in, opening the manufacturing of spare parts or upgrades.
- **Collaborative working** by stimulating open hardware academic and industrial cooperation, knowledge exchange and collective problem-solving, and amplifying the impact on future projects.

Considering the broad overlap of these impact areas with the stated missions of research universities and universities of applied sciences, the open hardware route should be systematically embraced and supported by these organizations.

The analysis of open science scholars and practitioners from their interaction with the existing knowledge transfer facilitation at the universities, however, indicate practical barriers and organizational challenges that need to be overcome. In a recent study involving open hardware stakeholders in academia, knowledge transfer offices (KTO) in EU, and TTOs in US, Dr. Julieta Arancioa have concluded that:

“If the technology being developed is deemed patentable it may generate a conflict with the tech transfer office [...] however patenting is expensive for universities and most of the time OSH designs are deemed non-patentable; as a result OSH is out of scope, and researchers often get no in-house support Open hardware falls in the gap between patentable vs technology with public outreach potential and therefore is usually not supported by university specialized services such as tech-transfer or science communications”.

The experts and administrators who have participated in this survey also mention the problem of choosing which platforms would be used for

sharing hardware, who owns maintenance of those platforms and how designs are preserved over time. Furthermore, there is no consensus on who should own the digital infrastructure.

Another critical evaluation at the Gathering for Open Hardware (GOSH-TTO-Brief-2021) summarizes the current situation as:

“TTO performance is currently evaluated against priorities and metrics that are usually based on the IP model, including key performance indicators (KPIs) such as revenue, number of patents filed, licenses agreed, spin-off companies established and external investment in those spin-offs. These metrics are not incompatible with open hardware licensing and its commercialisation; however, they do not easily align with the goals of open licensing. This misalignment can prevent TTO staff from advocating internally for exploring and ultimately adopting open hardware.”

And therefore, despite the inherent alignment of the goals of the open hardware practitioners and scientists with those of the TTO, the opportunities for collaboration and synergy are lost because of the lack of engagement and mismatch in the partnership approaches. To remove these barriers and release the great potential of open hardware for transferring impactful projects from the academic creators to their communities and societal beneficiaries, a collective effort at the national level is essential.

The following section proposes an approach to overcome the barriers and develop the opportunities mentioned previously.

5. CREATING AN OPEN-SOURCE HARDWARE ECOSYSTEM IN THE NETHERLANDS

A major advantage of developing open hardware solutions in the context of science is adopting a more transparent and accountable approach towards society when it comes to developing and delivering technology. We have discussed how open hardware supports the general idea and approach in open science that strives for a more reliable, robust, inclusive and collaborative scientific community. Acknowledging the need to consider open hardware as part of the work-culture of universities is a first step only. In order to significantly bring a societal impact it also needs to be embedded in institutions, education, and even the public common sense.

What do we mean by an ecosystem?

We mean a network of interconnected systems that may include policies, law, educational programmes, development programmes, incubation programmes, dedicated resources that may range from facilities, to funding of personnel and materials. Such an ecosystem should also be conceived as a community that observes and develops open source practices critically considering for example the limits and difficulties of open source practices in some contexts, industries or scenarios, and spot those sectors and cases where it becomes essential. For example there are obvious fields that are questionable from an ethical and societal point of view such as the development of open source weapons. But these exceptions must not blind us from the huge advantages that come with adoption of open sourcing. For example, the expiry of patents of 3D printing has brought major innovations that have transformed educational spaces⁵. Open source ventilators, which were developed during the COVID-19 pandemic, enabled replication and adaptation to local production needs to satisfy specific demands, and saved many lives.

Why do we need a well-maintained open-source hardware ecosystem today

In the experience of the authors, structural support of open hardware projects in Dutch universities is marginal, if not neglectable, despite emerging grassroots' developments and push from scientists and students. Of the many active open hardware projects in the Netherlands, only 14 are listed in the OSHWA certified list of open hardware. The main reason for this limited production of open-source hardware designs is unawareness of the large potentials they have and misalignment of university IP regulations with the credit system required for open-source projects, especially regarding hardware. Furthermore, the dominant (and

sometimes blindly accepted) push for protecting intellectual property through the secrecy route and non-disclosure contracts, undermine open-source initiatives as a viable route for knowledge transfer.

While open source technologies have profoundly transformed the research and development of technologies towards a more resilient, flexible, collaborative and collective approach, these developments are overseen in Dutch academia. This is the case even if we consider that many prominent, emblematic open source software and hardware developments were born from academic and research interests at the universities. The list ranges from software and hardware that powers Dutch infrastructure like GNU/Linux, Python (originated in the Netherlands), Arduino, and all sorts of 3D printers.

This contradiction begs the question why do we have heavily subsidized incubation programmes for patented technologies but no incubation programs for open source development? Clearly, universities should have incubation programmes and perhaps even “dream” teams of student associations that reward the development of open-source hardware products as much as universities support other ultra-competitive projects such as racing cars, racing boats, or exclusive partnership with companies based on non-disclosure agreements and exclusivity.

The open hardware ecosystem in the Netherlands is inevitably growing, since teachers, educators, researchers, and students are already keen on using many kinds of open-source hardware technologies from 3D printers to microcontrollers. The use of open hardware technologies and products such as 3D printers, microcontrollers, and development boards makes research projects and education more cost effective. Dutch academia and the economic sector is also benefiting from these developments. However, there is very little production of open-source hardware in the Netherlands, despite the richness of the R&D sector and advanced research activities taking place in the country. Our recommendation is to change this approach by design, which means to develop an open hardware program that fosters further growth of this ecosystem to a symbiotic relation with the global open science movement.

How could we develop such an ecosystem?

In this section we discuss components of a strategy that could be translated into a program further on. The components of such a strategy includes:

⁵ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780128039175000018>

- **Raising awareness and education:** Promote awareness and understanding of open hardware among researchers, students, and institutions through workshops, training programs, and educational materials. Encourage universities to integrate open hardware concepts into their curricula and provide support for courses and programs focused on open hardware development.
 - **Practical training:** Establish hands-on training programs that provide researchers and students with opportunities to work on open hardware projects. These programs can involve collaborative workshops, hackathons, or design challenges, allowing students to gain practical experience in developing open technologies and fostering a culture of innovation.
 - **Learning by doing:** Promote experiential learning opportunities, such as internships or research projects, where students can actively contribute to open hardware initiatives. Collaborate with industry partners, research institutions, or community organizations to provide students with real-world experiences in open technology development.
 - **Open Hardware Labs:** Establish and scale up dedicated open hardware labs or maker spaces within universities. These spaces should be equipped with tools, materials, and resources for students and staff members to design, prototype, and test open technologies. Facilitate open collaboration and knowledge sharing within these labs to foster a vibrant open hardware community.
 - **Curricular integration:** Universities should integrate open hardware concepts into their educational programs. This can include offering courses or modules specifically focused on open hardware development, where students learn about the principles, methodologies, and practical aspects of designing and building open technologies.
- **Funding and resources:** Allocate dedicated funding and resources to support open hardware projects, research programs, and national infrastructures. Some of these projects might need dedicated support (such as material characterization centers or prototyping spaces) but quite often cover many times their cost in the value they create for the other research programs. Establish grant schemes specifically for open hardware development and provide access to facilities, equipment, and materials required for prototyping and testing.
- **Incubation Programs:** Establish incubation programs that actively support open hardware projects, providing mentorship, guidance, and access to networks of experts and industry partners. Foster collaborations between academia, industry, and the open-source hardware community to accelerate the development and commercialization of open hardware solutions.
- **Fostering collaboration and sharing knowledge:** Encourage collaboration and knowledge sharing among researchers, students, and institutions working on open hardware projects. Facilitate the creation of online platforms, forums, and communities where participants can share designs, ideas, and best practices.
- **Regulatory Considerations:** Identify and address any legal and regulatory barriers that may hinder the development and adoption of open hardware, especially in the public-private partnership funding programs. Advocate for policies that promote openness, accessibility, and interoperability of open hardware solutions. Engage with policymakers, industry stakeholders, and legal experts

to ensure a favorable environment for open hardware innovation.

- **Intellectual Property (IP) Policies:** Develop IP policies that promote open hardware and encourage researchers and students to adopt open hardware licenses for their designs. Encourage universities to create a supportive environment that values open hardware contributions and rewards individuals and teams involved in open hardware projects.
- **Evaluation and Recognition:** Establish evaluation mechanisms to assess the impact and quality of open hardware projects. Recognize and reward individuals and teams involved in successful open hardware initiatives through awards, grants, and academic or public recognition.

By enacting these policies and initiatives, the Netherlands can foster an open hardware ecosystem that supports innovation, high-quality education, collaboration, and societal impact. This will contribute to the advancement of open science principles, enhance the country's research and development competencies, and promote a culture of openness and transparency in the academic and industrial sectors.

CONCLUSION

At the core of higher education and academic research lies the quest to improve the world around us. However, this goal can only be achieved if we take into account the challenges such as those of technology and ethics, inequalities, underdevelopment, unsustainable developments, to name just a few. In this context, we believe that open hardware, open source, and open science can be powerful tools to help overcome such challenges. By embracing open hardware, the Netherlands can solidify its position as a leader in open science and contribute to the global effort of achieving sustainable development goals.

Open hardware has numerous benefits for the Netherlands and the world. It can accelerate the transition of an invention into a useful product, reduce costs, and promote sustainable practices. By sharing hardware designs openly, we can democratize access to technology and facilitate collaborative innovation.

Our call to action is for all stakeholders to support open hardware initiatives, programmes, projects in the Netherlands, to help us create a better future for everyone. It is a duty, a privilege and an adventure to embrace openness, share knowledge and resources, because it is one of crucial vehicles we need to reach a more just, sustainable, and equitable world.

Open hardware is also good for science, as it enables more people and teams to access hardware designs and makes science more reproducible. It is good for education, as it provides students with hands-on learning opportunities and fosters creativity and innovation. And it is good for society, as it promotes sustainable development and reduces inequalities.

To develop open hardware, we need to combine bottom-up initiatives at universities with top-down governance from universities and research organizations. We need to create a flourishing ecosystem for open scientific hardware in the Netherlands that increases the quality and impact of research and education. We also need to critically, effectively and ethically bring openness to science, education and society, addressing also the cases where openness becomes a challenge or presents fundamental risks to society.

THE WAY FORWARD

Recommendations for creating the Dutch open-source hardware ecosystem

RIGHT NOW, to Start

- Recognize Open Hardware as a pillar in all policy documents related to open science
- Create challenges and funding calls for open-source hardware development
- Allocate a seed budget and form a taskforce for developing the national open-source hardware roadmap
- Identify open-source hardware equipment that can immediately serve education and research and create a national expertise center for supporting their adoption
- Identify and eliminate policies and practices that are unjustifiably opposing and hindering open-source hardware in grant application, knowledge transfer program, and research partnership agreements

NEXT, Go further

- Organize open-source hardware hubs and competency centers in all research units
- Create trainings for open hardware developers and researchers who want to increase the impact of their research products through open hardware
- Offer open hardware expertise to research group similar to the eScience center
- Incubate Research Hardware Engineers (RHEs) with open-source expertise
- Train and equip the Knowledge Transfer Offices to support open-source hardware entrepreneurship
- Embed open-source hardware assessments in evaluation of research projects
- Create a national Open Hardware Lab to identify research needs and maintain a database of open-source hardware solutions for interoperability and reproducibility

AND THEN, Sustain

- Create a national fund for providing open-source hardware to starting research teams
- Educate and support open-source hardware maintenance
- Educate researchers and support them for open-source hardware documentation
- Create Research Hardware Engineer roles for open source developers inside all universities
- Facilitate the development of OH standards
- Pursue replication projects both as a method of teaching and experimenting with developing open-source hardware
- Create pathways to make research outcome and equipment developed in projects open by default
- Facilitate good media recording for documentation and education of open-source hardware
- Facilitate using open-source hardware in citizen science projects for maximum impact.
- Extend the institutional capabilities of knowledge-transfer offices for supporting open-source entrepreneurship and business development
- Fully finance open-source hardware for urgent societal needs, such as in emerging sustainability transition technologies and solutions for adapting to climate-change

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